

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Hydrolysis of Acetamide in isoPropanol-Water Mixtures

M. M. ELSEMONGY, M. S. ABU ELAMAYEM, M. N. H. MOUSSA AND M. M. GOUDA

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University, Egypt

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The rate of acidic and alkaline hydrolysis was measured in the temperature range 25-50° in pure water and isopropanol-water mixtures up to 76% by weight of alcohol in acidic medium and to 50% by weight in alkaline medium. The velocity constant decreased with progressive addition of the organic solvent and it was higher in alkaline hydrolysis than in acidic hydrolysis. The isocomposition and isodielectric energies of activation were calculated and discussed in terms of solvation effects. The reaction rate was correlated with solvent composition. Dielectric constant effect on the reaction rate was investigated on the basis of Elsemongy's equations. The refined values of a_{\neq} (radius of the activated complex + radius of a water molecule) were calculated and are all within a reasonable range and change from 5.6 to 6.6 Å in the temperature range studied. However, these values account for the solvation of the activated complex and give an idea about the extent of solvation. Also, these values decrease with decrease of dielectric constant of the medium. This was discussed in terms of water structure and the large separating power of high dielectric media. Mechanisms for acidic and alkaline hydrolysis were proposed which account for the role and the effects of the solvent on reaction rate and these were confirmed by thermodynamic data.

ACIDIC and basic amide hydrolysis has been studied recently by several authors and has been discussed in reviews^{1,2}. Acidic and basic hydrolysis of acetamide and propionamide in ethanol-water mixtures has been studied by Laidler and Landskroener³. The rates were found to increase with increasing dielectric constant. This was explained in terms of the fact that the activated complexes were much polar than the reactants, so that their formation was enhanced by media of high dielectric constant. Kinetics of the acid hydrolysis of acetamide in dioxane-water mixtures has been studied by Koskikallio⁴. The first order rate constants of the hydrolysis of protonated acetamide were calculated from kinetic data and known acid constants of the amide over a wide range of dioxane-water mixtures. Alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in water containing methanol, glycol or glycerol up to about 50wt % was studied⁵ in the temperature range 25°-40°. The bimolecular velocity constant decreased while the energy of activation increased with alcohol addition. The effect per mole was more pronounced on ascending the polyalcohol series. Structure, medium and temperature dependence of acid-catalysed amide hydrolysis were discussed recently by Smith and Yates⁶. The kinetic acidity dependence and medium dependence of the activation parameters have been analysed. The rate constants of the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in various dioxane-water mixtures and tert. butanol-water mixtures were determined⁷ systematically at 25°-50°. The rate was favoured by an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium and passes by a minimum at 48.01% by weight of dioxane in the acidic hydrolysis. The isocomposition

and isodielectric energies of activation were calculated and the reaction rate was correlated with solvent composition. The calculated thermodynamic data and other parameters were discussed as evidences for the solvation effects and supporting the suggested mechanism.

The solvent effects on the kinetics of amide hydrolysis are subject to uncertainty. In this paper, the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in various water-isopropanol mixtures were studied, with the object to obtain an idea of the effect of solvent on the reaction rate and mechanism.

Experimental

Materials. The purification and preparation of acetamide, hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions were described before⁷. The isopropanol was purified by refluxing over stannous chloride for 2 hr to remove peroxides, and then over quicklime for 4 hrs. The isopropanol was fractionally distilled (b.p. 82.3°) discarding the first portions of the distillate until the test for acetone was negative. Boiled conductivity water was used throughout all the experimental work.

Kinetic procedure. The rate of saponification was measured in the temperature range 25°-50° in pure water and water-isopropanol mixtures up to 50% by weight. The rate of acidic hydrolysis was measured also in pure water in the temperature range 25°-50° and in water-isopropanol mixtures up to 76% by weight in the temperature range 35°-50°. The reaction mixtures were prepared and the rate of the reaction was followed by the methods described before⁷.

In the presence of isopropanol, the infinity values were determined and the readings were always constant and concordant with the calculated values and assured complete hydrolysis in the different isopropanol-water mixtures.

The kinetic equation. The hydrolysis of acetamide in an acidic or basic medium is a second order reaction, and the bimolecular rate constant is calculated according to the equation,

$$k_2 = \frac{x}{a(a-x)t}$$

where a is the initial concentration of both acetamide and acid or alkali and x is the amount decomposed at the time t . Calculation of the velocity constant

k_2 was carried out by plotting $\frac{x}{a-x}$ against t in hours

where straight lines passing through the origin were obtained. The slope of such lines (S) amounts to a k_2 , whence,

$$k_2 = S/a \text{ liter mole}^{-1} \text{ hr.}^{-1}$$

Results and Discussion

Velocity constant and energy of activation. The second-order rate constants in liter mole⁻¹ hr.⁻¹ for the acidic and basic hydrolysis of acetamide in water and isopropanol-water mixtures at 25°-50° were calculated from the slopes of the linear plots of $x/(a-x)$ against time, t . The rate constants at different temperatures and solvent compositions are collected

Fig. 1. Second order plots at 40° in isopropanol-water mixtures.

in Tables 1 and 3. Typical plots at 40° are shown in Figures 1 and 2 for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis respectively. In the temperature range studied, the reaction in isopropanol-water mixtures obeyed the Arrhenius equation fairly satisfactorily. The isocomposition and isodielectric energies of activation

Fig. 2. Second order plots at 40° in isopropanol-water mixtures.

(E_c and E_d) were calculated from plots of $\log k_2$ and $\log k_d$ against $1/T$, respectively. The values of E_c and E_d are given in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4.

TABLE 1. VELOCITY CONSTANTS (IN LITER MOLE⁻¹ HR⁻¹) AND ENERGY OF ACTIVATION IN ACIDIC ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt%	0.0	10.0	20.0	40.0	57.5	76
M/l	0.000	1.617	3.207	6.110	8.448	10.698
$t = 25^\circ$	0.0371	—	—	—	—	—
$= 35^\circ$	0.1035	0.0714	0.0581	0.0436	0.0388	0.0333
$= 40^\circ$	0.1667	0.1178	0.0973	0.0715	0.0646	0.0559
$= 50^\circ$	0.4217	0.2957	0.2425	0.1843	0.1667	0.1486
E_c k cal./mole	18.57	18.89	18.96	19.16	19.27	19.89

TABLE 2. ISODIELECTRIC ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION, E_d , IN ACIDIC ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Dielectric constant	10	30	50	60	70
E_d K cal/mole	20.27	19.84	19.43	21.66	21.75

TABLE 3. VELOCITY CONSTANTS AND ENERGY OF ACTIVATION IN ALKALINE ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Wt% M/l	0	10	20	30	40	50
$t = 25^\circ$	0.1361	0.1093	0.0844	0.0705	0.0638	0.0602
$= 35^\circ$	0.3103	0.2580	0.2000	0.1680	0.1536	0.1396
$= 40^\circ$	0.4681	0.3889	0.3083	0.2537	0.2262	0.2068
$= 50^\circ$	1.1176	0.8610	0.6379	0.5422	0.4784	0.4259
E_c k cal./ mole	16.07	15.99	15.85	15.66	15.38	15.04

The isocomposition energies of activation comprise the effect due to changes in the dielectric constant of the solvent with change of temperature. This effect fades away when the activation energies are cal-

TABLE 4. ISODIELECTRIC ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION, E_d , IN ALKALINE ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES

Dielectric constant	60	65	70	75	80
E_d k cal./mole	17.73	17.94	18.01	18.46	18.74

culated from the rate constants in isodielectric solutions and the contribution due to solvation phenomena will be mostly or partly eliminated.

In each of the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis, the velocity constant decreased with progressive addition of the organic solvent. However, the values of the velocity constant in alkaline hydrolysis were higher than those in acidic hydrolysis. On the other hand, the decrease in E_c in the alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in isopropanol-water mixtures may be attributed to solvation of the reactants to a lesser extent than the activated complex whereas the increase in E_c in the acidic hydrolysis represents the reverse effect. Table 2 shows that the isodielectric energy of activation of the acidic hydrolysis changes from 20.27 to 21.75 K cal./mole in the dielectric constant range of $D = 10-70$, and passes through a minimum at $D = 50$. In the light of Hyne's theory⁸, the presence of a minimum through which the energy of activation passes, is indicative of specific solvation effects for a system changing from the polar to the ionic form in the activated state.

Thermodynamic data of the activated complex. The effect of change in solvent composition on the rate and mechanism of the reaction is conveniently expressed in terms of the thermodynamic data of activation. These were calculated at the different temperatures for the different solvent compositions in acidic and alkaline hydrolysis and are compiled in Tables 5 and 6.

TABLE 5. THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN ACIDIC ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES. ΔF^\ddagger AND ΔH^\ddagger IN K cal./mole, $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ IN cal. mole/degree

Wt % isopropanol	0.0	10.0	20.0	40.0	57.5	76.0
35°	ΔF^\ddagger	24.47	24.69	24.82	25.00	25.07
	ΔH^\ddagger	17.96	18.28	18.35	18.35	18.66
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	21.13	20.80	21.00	20.93	20.80
40°	ΔF^\ddagger	24.58	24.79	24.91	25.10	25.17
	ΔH^\ddagger	17.95	18.27	18.34	18.54	18.65
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	21.17	20.82	20.98	20.95	20.82
50°	ΔF^\ddagger	24.79	25.01	25.14	25.32	25.38
	ΔH^\ddagger	17.93	18.25	18.32	18.52	18.63
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	21.23	20.92	20.49	21.04	20.89

TABLE 6. THERMODYNAMIC DATA IN ALKALINE ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES. ΔF^\ddagger AND ΔH^\ddagger IN K cal./mole, $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ IN cal./mole/degree

Wt % isopropanol	0	10	20	30	40	50
25°	ΔF^\ddagger	23.49	23.62	23.77	23.88	23.94
	ΔH^\ddagger	15.48	15.40	15.26	15.07	14.79
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	26.87	27.57	28.54	29.55	30.69
35°	ΔF^\ddagger	23.79	23.91	24.06	24.17	24.22
	ΔH^\ddagger	15.46	15.38	15.24	15.05	14.77
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	27.03	27.68	28.62	29.60	30.67
40°	ΔF^\ddagger	23.93	24.05	24.19	24.31	24.39
	ΔH^\ddagger	15.45	15.37	15.23	15.04	14.76
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	27.08	27.72	28.61	29.60	30.75
50°	ΔF^\ddagger	24.16	24.33	24.52	24.62	24.70
	ΔH^\ddagger	15.43	15.35	15.21	15.02	14.74
	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	27.02	27.79	28.81	29.71	30.82

It is seen that ΔF^\ddagger increases gradually with increase of isopropanol concentration in both acidic and alkaline hydrolysis. According to the theory of absolute reaction rates, the increase in ΔF^\ddagger is a sign of solvation of the reacting species. Therefore, solvation is expected to be more pronounced in presence of isopropanol. The variation of ΔS^\ddagger with solvent composition does not follow a linear relationship in acidic and alkaline media. This non-linear behaviour is a criterion⁹ of specific solvation and shows that the random orientation of the two components is not valid. The heat content change, ΔH^\ddagger , increases in acidic hydrolysis whereas it decreases gradually in alkaline hydrolysis by successive addition of isopropanol. The $-\Delta S^\ddagger$ values were higher in alkaline isopropanol-water mixtures and ΔF^\ddagger values were higher in acidic isopropanol-water mixtures.

Effect of water concentration. To investigate the role of water in the solvation process, $\log k_2$ was plotted against $\log[H_2O]$, (Tables 7 and 8) where upon straight lines were obtained. In both acidic

TABLE 7. VARIATION OF VELOCITY CONSTANT WITH DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND WATER CONCENTRATION IN ACIDIC MEDIUM

Wt%	0.0	10.0	20.0	40.0	57.5	76.0
$\log[H_2O]$	1.745	1.686	1.632	1.484	1.319	1.048
35°						
D	74.87	68.05	61.05	47.21	35.05	24.18
$2+\log k_2$	1.0149	0.8534	0.7640	0.6393	0.5890	0.5228
40°						
D	73.12	66.33	59.56	45.86	34.10	23.50
$2+\log k_2$	1.2219	1.0712	0.9879	0.8543	0.8103	0.7474
50°						
D	69.85	63.12	56.61	43.54	32.30	22.10
$2+\log k_2$	1.6250	1.4708	1.3847	1.2655	1.2219	1.1721

TABLE 8. VARIATION OF VELOCITY CONSTANT WITH DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND WATER CONCENTRATION IN ALKALINE MEDIUM

Wt%	0	10	20	30	40	50
$\log[H_2O]$	1.745	1.686	1.632	1.564	1.484	1.394
25°						
D	78.45	71.39	64.13	56.94	49.75	42.50
$2+\log k_2$	1.1338	1.0386	0.9264	0.8482	0.8048	0.7799
35°						
D	74.87	68.05	61.05	54.13	47.21	40.24
$2+\log k_2$	1.4918	1.4116	1.3010	1.2253	1.1864	1.1449
40°						
D	73.12	66.33	59.56	52.71	45.86	39.16
$2+\log k_2$	1.6703	1.5898	1.4890	1.4043	1.3545	1.3156
50°						
D	69.85	63.12	56.61	50.18	43.54	37.03
$2+\log k_2$	2.0481	1.9350	1.8047	1.7342	1.6798	1.6293

and alkaline hydrolysis two linear portions separated by a sharp boundary at a water concentration of 39.81 moles/liter (71.66%) were shown in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. Above this water content the slope of the lines amounted to 2 while below this content the slope amounted to mean values of 0.25 and 0.5 in the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis

respectively. This means that, in water-rich solvents, two water molecules are involved in the formation

Fig. 3. Variation of velocity constant with water concentration.

of the activated complex. However, at higher isopropanol contents, the number of water molecules is decreased to 0.25 and 0.5 in acidic and alkaline media respectively. The result means that the internal structure of the medium suffered serious changes on addition of isopropanol to water.

A similar behaviour was observed in the work of Tommila and coworkers on the solvolysis of alkyl halides and benzene sulphonates in various dioxane-water mixtures¹⁰⁻¹², where two linear regions with different slopes were observed. They stated that the hydrogen bond between a dioxane and water molecules is stronger than that between two water molecules. Thus hydrogen bonding between neighbouring water molecules will be replaced gradually by hydrogen bonding with dioxane molecules, and when there are about two water molecules per organic solvent molecule, the tetrahedral structure of water is then largely broken. Further addition of the organic solvent causes water to associate more and more in groups containing only one water and one organic solvent molecules, and statistically distributed among free organic solvent molecules. The internal structure of the medium in the two regions is, therefore, essentially different, and this explains their different behaviour towards hydrolysis.

The exact nature of liquid water is not so far well understood¹³. However, there is a general agreement that it is a very highly structured liquid¹⁴. Many

of its properties suggest that it is a mixture of fluctuating regions of three dimensional hydrogen-bonded polymers in equilibrium with randomly arranged H_2O monomer molecules¹⁵. At normal

is then opposed by further addition of alcohol, so that the structure-making passes through a maximum.

From the above discussion it is possible to correlate the reaction rate with solvent composition as follows :

1. From 100 to 71.66 wt.% of water the rate decreases because of two factors; (a) the decrease in water concentration, and (b) the decrease in the fraction of the free water molecules due to the fact that addition of solvent causes the hydrogen bonding between water molecules to be replaced by the stronger hydrogen bonding between water and alcohol molecules. The net result is that the rate decreases and the slope of $\log k$ versus $\log [H_2O]$ is 2.

2. From 71.66 to 50 wt. % of water the decrease in reaction rate is less pronounced than in the previous region and the slopes of the lines decrease to 0.5 and 0.25 in the alkaline and acidic media respectively. This may be due to the fact that on gradual addition of isopropanol the tetrahedral structure of water has been largely broken, further addition of isopropanol molecules, although resulting in a decrease in water concentration, will be hydrogen-bonded with each other, and will have little effect on the free water molecules. Hence the availability of the water molecules in this range of solvent composition is greater than that in the previous region (in which any slight addition of isopropanol will capture water molecules through stronger hydrogen bonding). This effect will compensate part of the effect due to the decrease in water concentration and the net decrease in rate will be less than that in the previous range.

Fig. 4. Variation of velocity constant with water concentration.

temperature and pressure pure aliphatic alcohols also have a considerable fraction of their molecules joined in rings and chains, but they do not seem to participate in the formation of three dimensional clusters characteristic of water¹⁴.

It was supposed¹⁴ that when an alcohol is added to pure water, the structure of the latter would be destroyed progressively as the alcohol content increases. However, the maxima and minima observed by Arnett and coworkers¹⁴, in ΔH^\ddagger for solvolysis in this solvent mixture led them to suggest that the structure breaking must go through a maximum in high water region of the solvent. These authors stated, however, that if the only effect of adding alcohol to water was to break down its structure, this would be expected to reach gradually a plateau, and then level off until nearly pure alcohol was reached. At this point the disrupting effect of adding water on the structure of pure alcohol begins to be operative.

It was proved in many instances, however, that the first addition of an alcohol to water causes at first an increase in the degree of solvent structuredness¹¹. This structure-making effect becomes saturated sooner the larger the alcohol molecules. It

Effect of dielectric constant. The dielectric constant values for the isopropanol-water mixtures in the temperature range 25°-50° were adopted from Akerlof's data¹⁶ by interpolation from large-scale plots. Plot of $\log k_2$ versus D values given in Tables 7 and 8 gave straight lines of positive slopes. A typical plot for the acidic hydrolysis is shown in Figure 5. It is easily observed that there are two linear portions separated by a sharp boundary at each temperature. It is evident that Elsemongy's equation¹⁷ is obeyed for each linear part in the alcohol- and water-rich regions. The refined values of a_{\ddagger} (radius of the activated complex + constant) were obtained by using the same procedure mentioned before¹⁷. These are given in Tables 9 and 10. The values of a_{\ddagger} obtained are all within a reasonable range and change from 5.6 to 6.6 Å in the dielectric constant range of $D = 10-80$ and in the temperature range of 25°-50°. At any given temperature the value of a_{\ddagger} decreases with decreasing water concentration. For certain composition the a_{\ddagger} value increases with increase of temperature. However, these values account for the solvation of the activated complex and give an idea about the extent of solvation. Considering the mechanism of the reaction (which is given below) the radius of the activated complex may be calculated where a_{\ddagger} is equal to the radius of the activated complex plus the radius of a water molecule.

It is evident that the values of a_{\neq} decrease with decrease of dielectric constant i.e. decrease by progressive addition of the organic solvent. This is in agreement with the fact that on progressive addition

Fig. 5. Influence of dielectric constant on k_2 .

TABLE 9. REFINED VALUES OF a_{\neq} FOR ACIDIC ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES IN Å

t°C \ D	10	30	50	60	70
35	5.7	5.9	6.0	6.4	6.5
40	5.7	5.9	6.0	6.4	6.5
50	5.8	6.0	6.1	6.5	6.6

TABLE 10. REFINED VALUES OF a_{\neq} FOR ALKALINE ISOPROPANOL-WATER MIXTURES IN Å

t°C \ D	60	65	70	75	80
25	5.6	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.7
35	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.8
40	5.7	5.7	5.7	5.8	5.8
50	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.9	5.9

of the organic solvent, the structure of water would be destroyed progressively and the reacting species

might become closer to each other and so the distance of closest approach a_{\neq} would be decreased. Considering the hydration number for each of the hydrogen ion (4) and the hydroxide ion (3) one should expect more solvation in the acidic hydrolysis and therefore the a_{\neq} values would be higher than that in alkaline hydrolysis. Besides we may mention the known facts regarding the large separating power of high dielectric media.

Proposed mechanism. In the light of the above considerations, mechanisms for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide should account satisfactorily for the role and the effects of the solvent on the reaction rate. It was noticed that successive addition of the organic solvent alters the rate without influencing the mechanism and so the mechanism is the same for the different solvent compositions. The analogies between the kinetic behaviour of acetamide in acidic and alkaline isopropanol-water mixtures and that in acidic and alkaline dioxane-water mixtures⁷ support our previous proposed mechanisms for the acidic and alkaline hydrolysis of acetamide in dioxane-water mixtures. Other evidences for these bimolecular mechanisms are the large negative values of the activation entropy ($-\Delta S^\ddagger = 32.15-19.98$ cal mole⁻¹ degree⁻¹) and the values of energy of activation ($E_c = 15.04-19.89$ K cal. mole⁻¹). These values are in excellent agreement with our previous proposed bimolecular mechanisms and support it.

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